

Analysis of Between Ideal and Utopic in The Short Story "Dongeng Tarka And Sarka": Studied by The Cooperation Concept Of Jean-Luc Nancy by M. Hafidzulloh S. M

Anugrah Yusuf Avriarno
Aqua Culture – IPB University
anugrah.yusuf354@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is analyzing the ideals and utopics in the short story "Tarka and Sarka tales" in this case humans on earth are a form of *dasein* communality that has created groups and created the concept of being-in-together. The existence of the concept of being-in-together as objects continue to move forward and create ideal conditions, in this situation the concept of a Literary Utopia emerges, in which human life continues to share in togetherness. By sharing the meaning of life, it is possible to lead to an ideal condition, a fantasy of a better life for humans using a key, namely a sense of brotherhood. On the other hand, an ideal situation is a condition where a community is headed in a point of view that has not been fully discussed.

Keywords: *utopia, being-in-together, ideal*

INTRODUCTION

A social life wrapped by a state of togetherness shows the existence of a form of compearance that serves to explain human togetherness from a plural and singular point of view because humans are together in togetherness from both points of view in their being-in-togetherness. The form of compearance is a resistance of several data collected in one place. The *dasein* association is to form an impression that is used as a development between the plural and the singular. The resistance will not erase the concept of human standing even if he merges into a certain resistance.

From what she got, Nancy uses the concept of an inoperative society which juts out into the impossibility of achieving meaning and answering problems under certain conditions. Because of this impossibility, humans communicate in order to create concrete answers. Therefore, the significance of meaning is a conceptual step that prioritizes the role of humans in the modern era. What causes the meaning that is produced is never finished and always appears this is also known as *literary utopia*.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer uses for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. This analysis is carried out by identifying the ideal and the utopian by presenting the construction of a permanent singularity, being-in-together with the point of view of Jean-Luc Nancy.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are the condition that has been shown in the story is that the existence of several characters in the story is not just born in the world. Their existence is involved with other characters because there is a togetherness that makes them interact with each other. Neither their involvement as citizens of the Hastina Kingdom or the interaction between Tarka and Sarka with his father.

From this it can be seen that the incompleteness of several characters in this short story have not had the opportunity to go to a certain dimension. The inability to achieve certain dimensions makes the dasein consisting of several figures including Tarka and Sarka continue to make meaning and idealize life. Their existence has become a communal identity. Because of the communal identity, this community is a symbol of impossibility that will continue to be used in understanding certain meanings.

The purpose of a this analysis of papers in the form of discussions are in the process towards an ideal for change is a condition that is difficult to realize. On the other hand, since humans live as entities with social backgrounds, they will always lead a dynamic life. Because of this dynamism, the meaning of life will continue to form in a process approaching the ideal so that the ideal dimension becomes a utopian dimension whose existence is unknown.

This series of processes enables people to continue to achieve what they dream of. Therefore, the dynamics of life with human activities are formed with various utopias for the future. Because utopia is something that is utopian, the idealized state in the future will always be a collective desire, and cause conditions for discursive struggle.

CONCLUSION

For how the writer subjectively see from the paper analysis that from the above explanation the concept of being-in-together is a community formed from several daseins, in which case they are

not planned to be born in the world. The formation of a community causes *dasein* to exist in togetherness but does not form a plural identity. The indication in this story is that the Tarka and Sarka families with the royal circles have different dimensions. That difference is what makes their singularity symbol even in a pluralistic life situation.

REFERENCES

- Altman, R. (2021). 3. A Semantic/Syntactic Approach to film genre. In *Film genre reader IV* (pp. 27-41). University of Texas Press.
- Barus, I. R. G., Simanjuntak, M. B., & Resmayasari, I. (2021). READING LITERACIES THROUGH EVIETA-BASED LEARNING MATERIAL: STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS (Study Case Taken from Vocational School–IPB University). *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(1), 15-20.
- Bateman, J., & Schmidt, K. H. (2013). *Multimodal film analysis: How films mean*. Routledge.
- Bednarek, M. (2015). Corpus-assisted multimodal discourse analysis of television and film narratives. In *Corpora and discourse studies* (pp. 63-87). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Bellour, R. (2000). *The analysis of film*. Indiana University Press.
- Benshoff, H. (2015). *Film and television analysis: An introduction to methods, theories, and approaches*. Routledge.
- Bernadtua, M., Rafli, Z., & Boeriswati, E. (2022, January). LANGUAGES ACQUISITION AND TEACHING IN KELAPA GADING–NORTH JAKARTA (CASE STUDY TAKEN AT SAINT PETER'S JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL). In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 162-170).
- Bittau, F., Potamialis, C., Togay, M., Abbas, A., Isherwood, P. J., Bowers, J. W., & Walls, J. M. (2018). Analysis and optimisation of the glass/TCO/MZO stack for thin film CdTe solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 187, 15-22.
- Carr, D. (2019). Methodology, representation, and games. *Games and Culture*, 14(7-8), 707-723.
- Condon, W. S., & Ogston, W. D. (1966). Sound film analysis of normal and pathological behavior patterns. *Journal of nervous and mental disease*.
- Estrada, L. M., Hielscher, E., Koolen, M., Olesen, C. G., Noordegraaf, J., & Blom, J. (2017). Film analysis as annotation: Exploring current tools. *Moving Image: The Journal of the Association of Moving Image Archivists*, 17(2), 40-70.
- Franco, A., Magnani, A., & Maio, D. (2020). A multimodal approach for human activity recognition based on skeleton and RGB data. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 131, 293-299.
- Geiger, J., & Rutsky, R. L. (Eds.). (2013). *Film analysis: A Norton reader*. WW Norton & Company.

- Henseler, C. (2021). Finding Humanity. *The Scholar as Human: Research and Teaching for Public Impact*, 129.
- Jahn, M. (2003). A guide to narratological film analysis. *Poems, Plays, and Prose: A Guide to the Theory of Literary Genres*, 2.
- Kendrick, M. (2016). *Literacy and multimodality across global sites*. Routledge.
- Kozlarek, O. (2015). Introduction: Crossing Borders, Reaching Humanity. In *Octavio Paz* (pp. 9-16). transcript-Verlag.
- Liu, A. A., Xu, N., Nie, W. Z., Su, Y. T., Wong, Y., & Kankanhalli, M. (2016). Benchmarking a multimodal and multiview and interactive dataset for human action recognition. *IEEE Transactions on cybernetics*, 47(7), 1781-1794.
- Lo, H. F., Wu, I. W., & Ni, C. C. (2018, July). Representation of Memory in Design for Humanity. In *International Conference on Cross-Cultural Design* (pp. 43-57). Springer, Cham.
- Magnusson, P., & Godhe, A. L. (2019). Multimodality in Language Education--Implications for Teaching. *Designs for Learning*, 11(1), 127-137.
- Parc, J. (2018). Evaluating the effects of protectionism on the film industry: A case study analysis of Korea. In *Handbook of State Aid for Film* (pp. 349-366). Springer, Cham.
- Pattiwael, A. S. (2019). Literature for Developing Student's Humanity Awareness. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 79-88).
- Peña-Cervel, M. S. (2016). Motivating film title translation: a cognitive analysis. *CÍRCULO de Lingüística Aplicada a la Comunicación*, 66, 31.
- Plate, L. (2015). How to do things with literature in the digital age: Anne Carson's Nox, multimodality, and the ethics of bookishness. *Contemporary Women's Writing*, 9(1), 93-111.
- Richards, M. (2016). Film Music Themes: Analysis and Corpus Study. *Music Theory Online*, 22(1).
- Rosenberg, F. J. (2016). *After Human Rights: Literature, Visual Arts, and Film in Latin America, 1990-2010*. University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Rouast, P. V., Adam, M. T., & Chiong, R. (2019). Deep learning for human affect recognition: Insights and new developments. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 12(2), 524-543.
- Santos, R. B., & de Oliveira, U. R. (2019). Analysis of occupational risk management tools for the film and television industry. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 72, 199-211.
- Serafini, F. (2015). Multimodal literacy: From theories to practices. *Language Arts*, 92(6), 412-423.

- Simanjuntak, M. B. (2021). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “AUT BOI NIAN” WRITTEN BY WERVIN PANGGABEAN. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(1), 34-39.
- Simanjuntak, M. B. ., Suseno, M., Ramdhoni, R., Mayuni, I. ., Zuriyati, Z., & Sutrisno, S. (2022). The Value of Parents’ Image in Seven Batak Toba Songs (Literary Art Study). *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 6(2), 8540–8551.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., & Barus, I. R. G. (2020). English Reading Literacies to Improve Values Among Teenagers. *SELTICS*, 93-102.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., & Lumingkewas, M. S. (2022). THE WOMAN IN THE BOOK OF KINGS (LITERARY STUDIES AND HERMENEUTICS). In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 328-334).
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Barus, I. R. G., & Resmayasari, I. (2021). ANALYSIS OF VIOLENCE IN CITY OF GOD FILM DIRECTED BY FERNANDO MEIRELLES. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(1), 1-6.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Barus, I. R. G., & Resmayasari, I. (2021). Analysis of Song" Tanganku Na Metmet" by Using Translation Techniques into English. In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 195-202).
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Lumingkewas, M. S., & Sutrisno, S. (2021). ANALYSIS OF TANGIANG ALE AMANAMI (OUR FATHER) USING THE TECHNIQUES OF TRANSLATION. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(2), 70-75.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Rahmat, A. ., Setiadi, S. ., Suseno, M. ., Romdani, R., & Lumingkewas, M. S. . (2022). Power Relations in the Story of “Nommensen Bertemu Raja Panggalamei” by Patar Pasaribu. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 6(2), 8552–8557.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Suseno, M., & Setiadi, S. (2022). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MICROSOFT OFFICE 365 AS AN ONLINE ENGLISH LEARNING MEDIA. In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 25-32).
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Suseno, M., Setiadi, S., Lustyantie, N., & Barus, I. R. G. R. G. (2022). Integration of Curricula (Curriculum 2013 and Cambridge Curriculum for Junior High School Level in Three Subjects) in Pandemic Situation. *Ideas: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial, dan Budaya*, 8(1), 77-86.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Sutrisno, S., & Lumingkewas, M. S. (2021). LITERARY STUDY “NOMMENSEN, APOSTLE IN BATAKNESE”. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(2), 42-45.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Zuriyati, Z., & Lustyantie, N. (2022). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “JUJUNG GOARHI AMANG”(STUDY OF PORTRAY OF PARENTS). *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)*, 5(1), 236-243.

- Simanjuntak, M. B., Zuriyati, Z., Utami, S. R., & Lumingkewas, M. S. (2022). Nommensen and Bataknese (The Representation of Apostle). *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(2), 9291-9297.
- Sleman, S. M., & Fahmi, I. M. (2020). The Destiny of Humanity in the Future Cities of Ray Bradbury. *Zanco Journal of Humanity Sciences*, 24(1), 278-288.
- Teixeira, M. B. M., da Costa Galvao, L. L., Mota-Santos, C. M., & Carmo, L. J. O. (2020). Women and work: film analysis of Most Beautiful Thing. *Revista de Gestão*.
- Way, L. C., & McKerrell, S. (2017). *Music as multimodal discourse: Semiotics, power and protest*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Wellek, R. (2018). *The attack on literature and other essays*. UNC Press Books.
- Widjayanti, E. P. (2019). Building Humanity Values Through Maya Angelou's poems. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 143-148).
- Wildfeuer, J. (2014). *Film discourse interpretation: Towards a new paradigm for multimodal film analysis*. Routledge.
- Wu, J., & Yan, Y. (2016, November). Study of humanity teaching model in higher vocational school Chinese teaching. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Management Science, Education Tecnology, Arts, Social Science and Economics* (Vol. 85, pp. 1855-1858).